

BOLADA INTELEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada bolalarda intellektning rivojlanishi va shakllantirish yo'llari haqida ma'lumotlar yoritib o'tilgan. Bola dunyoga kelmasidan boshlab unga yo'nalish berib boorish, intellektini shakllantirish uchun qilinishi kerak bo'lgan ishlar haqida ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Annotation

This article provides information about the development and ways of establishing intelligence in children. From the moment a child is born, guiding him or her toward development, indicating the work that needs to be done to develop his or her own intelligence.

Tayanch so'zlar: intellekt, fatzand, bola, qobiiyat, ota-ona, dunyoqarash, maqsad, mehnat, o'qish, kitob, faoliyat, vaqt, tafakkur, tasavvur

Keywords: intelligence, children, child, ability, parent, mindset, goal, effort, reading, book, activity, time, thoughtfulness, imagination

Intelekt odatda bizning nazdimizda murakkab bir qobiliyatdek bir sòz bilan aytganda xalq nazdida ilohiy istedoddek tuyiladi. Ammo biz bilmaymizki bu ilohiy qobiliyat yoki noyob istedod emas balki barcha shaxsda bòlishi mumkin bòlgan aniqrogi bor bòlgan va vaqtlar ta'siri ostida yo'q bo'lib ketgan bir holat desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Odatda Ota onalar farzandining intellektini shakllantirish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish uchun farzandini turli xil qo'shimcha darslarga(amaliyot darslariga) yo'naltirishadi. Balki bu ularning fikricha to'g'ri xulosadir. Lekin aslida esa bolaga Ota onachalik ustozlik qila oladigan inson bo'lmaydi. Har qanday Ota onaning farzandi bu uning qilgan mehnatining mahsulidir. Xalqimizda bir naql bor "bola boshidan" bu nail qaysidir ma'nolarda to'g'ri lekin Ota ona bolasida ko'rishni xoxlagan qobiliyat, intellektni hali u dunyoga kelmasidan poydevorini qo'yishi kerak bo'ladi.

Agar farzandi ziyoli bo'lishini xohlasa ayol xomiladorlik paytida asosiy vaqtini ilmga, o'qishga, o'rganishga bag'ishlashi kerak bo'ladi. Agar farzandi mohir bir tikuvchi yoki shunga o'xshash kasb egasi bo'lishini xohlasa ayol xomiladorlik vaqtidanoq shu ishlarga Mehr berishi ko'p vaqtini shu hunarlarga baxshida etishi lozim. Shu fikrimning isbotini o'zim ko'rish maqsadida bir yil izlandim va

ikki xomilador ayolning xomiladorlik davri va farzandi dunyoga kelganidan keyingi bir yilni obdon kuzatdim. Birinchi ayol vujudiga farzand degan bebaho ne'mat paydo bo'lishidan oldin ham doimiy izlanib o'qib o'rganib yurgan. O'zining kasbini sevib boq vaqtini shu kasbiga bag'ishlab yurgan vaqt uning vujudida bir tirik jon paydo bo'ladi. Shunday baxtli kunlarning birida u ayol oliygohga o'qishga kiradi va yanada ilmga bo'lgan mehri ortib boradi. Farzandi tug'ilishining so'nggi kunigacha ilm, bilim, o'qish, izlanish bilan band bo'ladi. Va nihoyat farzand dunyoga keldi. Unga Ota onasi tomonidan chiroyli ism qo'yildi va shu ismga munosib farzand bo'lishi uchun ayol ilk kundan unga chiroyli tarbiya berishni boshladi. Boshqalarning nazarida bu balki kulguli holatdir ammo ayol chaqaloqning chillalik davridan boshlab unga kitoblar o'qib berar, jajji qo'lchalariga kitob, ruchkalar tutqizib yuradi. Farzang kun sayin o'sib boradi va jismlarni taniy boshlaganida unga oila a'zolari va yaqin qarindoshlari tomonidan turli xil o'yinchoqlar sovg'alar olib kelinadi, tabiiyki bola ularga qiziqadi, o'ynashni boshlaydi ammo bu o'yin uzoqqa cho'zilmaydi. Eng ko'p o'ynagan o'yinchog'ining vaqti 1 yoki 2 daqiqa bo'ladi. Ziyrak ona buni darhol o'z nazoratiga olib unga yo'nalish bera boshlaydi. Kunlarning birida ayol farzandining oldiga uch narsani qo'yadi: pul, o'yinchoqlar, daftar ruchka. O'z fikrining isbotini ko'rsatish maqsadida oldiga oila a'zolaridan birini chaqiradi va o'yinchoqlarning eng sarasini, pulni ham bezaklar yordamida bezatib, hajmini ham kengroq ko'rsatib ikkinchi tomoniga qo'yadi va nihoyat uchunchi eng uzoq joyga oddiygina bir daftar va ruchkani qo'yadi va farzandiga "bolam tanla qaysi birini olasan" deya o'zining onalik mehri bilan tushuntiradi. Bola esa hech qayerga qaramasdan to'g'ri daftar ruchka tomon emaklay boshlaydi. Buni ko'rgan yaqinlari onaning fikri to'g'rilinega, bola hozirdan ilmga mehr qo'yganiga ishonch hosil qiladi. Yangi, xashamdor, dabdabali o'yinchoqlarni 1 yo 2 daqiqa o'ynab zerikadigan bola oldiga daftar, ruchka, kitob va shunga o'xshash darslik anjomlarini bersa soatlab ularni sinchkovlik bilan kuzatib o'tiradi. Mana tez orada bu qizaloq bir yoshga to'ladi va hali hamon onasi bolasiga o'qish, yozish va eng asosiysi chiroyli eshtishni o'rgatib keladi.

Kuzatuvda bo'lgan ikkinchi xomilador ayol esa ro'zg'or ishlari va dehqonchilik ishlari bilan band bo'ladi. Xomiladorlik vaqti bir marotaba ham qo'lga kitob olmaydi va hattoki yozmaydi ham, faqat dehqonchilik ishlari, uy ro'zg'or yumishlari bilan band bo'ladi. Nihoyat 9 oy o'tib farzand dunyoga keladi. Bu ayol ham qiz farzand ko'radi.

Farzand tug'lganidan keyingi bir yil bu ayolda ham kuzatiladi bu ayolning farzandi o'yinchoqlar o'ynash, kitob, qog'ozlarni o'ynashni emas aksincha

doimiy harakatda bo'lishni o'ziga maqul ko'radi. Ota onasi bilan doim birga yurgan bu qizaloq mehnatga moyil, doimiy jismoniy harakat qilishga intiladi... Bu ikki qizning faoliyatini hali hamon kuzataman va so'zlarimning to'g'riligiga har tahlil qilish vaqtida yana ham amin bo'lamanki bolada intellekt, qobiliyatni shakllantirish uchun uni maktabdan bo'sh vaqtlari qo'shimcha mashg'ulotlarga berib emas, balki, u dunyoga kelmasidan oldin harakat qilish kerak. Bola dunyoga kelganidan so'ng uning intellektual qobiliyatini shakllantirish u yashayotgan, u tarbiya topayotgan atrof muhitga bog'liq bo'lib qoladi. Oila tarbiyasi ayniqsa oilada farzandga Ota onaning berayotgan to'g'ri tarbiyasi uning barcha qobiliyatlarini(yashirin bo'lgan qobiliyatlarini) ham rivojlanishiga yordam beradi. Asosiy ro'lni o'ynaydi desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Intellektual rivojlanish insonning ongi, tasavvuri va tafakkuri bilan bevosita bog'liq hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga insonning intellekti turli funksiyalarni o'z ichiga qamrab oladi. Ya'ni insondagi aqliy qobiliyatni yuqorida aytib o'tganimdek, dunyoqarashni va madaniyatni. Bularning barchasi bir maromda bo'lsa insondagi intellekt rivojlanishi o'sa boshlaydi.

Intelligence usually seems like a divine talent in our eyes, in one word, as a sophisticated ability. Nevertheless, we do not know whether it is a divine ability or a unique talent but it is not an exaggeration to say that it is a case of all people having certain abilities that they can have, and which have disappeared under the influence of time. Usually, parents' guide their child to various extracurricular activities (practical classes) in order to develop their child's ability to develop the intellect. Maybe this is the right conclusion, from their perspective. However, there wouldn't be anyone who could mentor a child as a parent, indeed. Any parent's child is the fruit of their work. We have a popular saying, "A child from the very beginning," which is true in a sense, but the ability, the intelligence that parents want to see in their child will have to be developed before the child is even born.

If a woman wants her child to be an intelligent person, during pregnancy she will have to dedicate most of her time to science, study, and learning. A woman must devote a lot of time to these activities from the beginning of her pregnancy if she wants her child to be an accomplished tailor or a similar profession. I spent a year researching this perspective to see for myself, and I observed the pregnancy period of two pregnant women and the year after the birth of their child. The first woman, even before having a priceless child in her body, was constantly searching and learning. The moment she falls in love with her profession and devotes her free time to that profession, a living soul appears

in her body. During one of these happy days, she applies to the university, and her love for science grows. Until the last day of the child's birth, she will be busy with science, studying, learning, and research. Finally, the baby is born. The parents gave her a beautiful name, which she deserved, and her mother began to give her a beautiful nurturing from day one. It is probably a ridiculous situation in everyone's eyes, but her mother has been reading books to her since she was a baby, and the baby walks around holding books and pens. The child grows every day, and as she begins to recognize the physical objects, they bring her various toys-gifts from family members and close relatives, of course, the child is interested in them, begins to play but this game does not last long. The time the toy plays the most is 1-2 minutes. The discerning mother immediately notices it and begins to give her direction. One day a woman puts three things in front of her child: money, toys, a notebook and a pen. In order to prove her point, she calls one of the family members to her and puts firstly, the toys on the second side, the money decorated with jewelry, with much larger size, and finally, on the third furthest place she simply puts the notebook and pen and explains to her child with her motherly love: "Choose, my dear, which of these you will take". And the child begins to crawl straight to the pen and notebook without looking anywhere. Seeing this, the loved ones will be convinced that the mother's opinion is correct, that the child has fallen in love with science from now on. A child who is bored playing with new, fancy, luxurious toys for 1-2 minutes sit for hours, watching them closely while she gives them a notebook, pen, book and similar learning tools. Here is this girl will soon be one year old, and still a mother will teach her child to read, write, and most importantly, beautiful to hear.

On the other hand, the second pregnant woman under observation will be busy with agriculture and farming. During her pregnancy, she never once picks up a book or even writes but is busy with farm chores and household chores. Finally, after nine months, a child is born. This woman will also have a daughter.

One year after birth, it is also observed that this woman's child prefers not to play with toys, books, and papers, but instead to be in constant motion. This girl, who always walks with her parents, is prone to childbirth, tends to constant physical activities.

I still follow the performance of these two girls and I am even more convinced of the accuracy of my words at each analysis to form a child's intelligence, abilities, it is necessary not to give him/her to additional classes in his/her free time from school but to act before he/she comes into the world.

After a child is born, the formation of his intellectual abilities becomes dependent on the environment in which s/he lives, in which s/he is brought up. Family nurturing especially in the family proper raising a child's parents help to develop all of the child's abilities as well(abilities that are hidden). It is no exaggeration to say that it plays a major role. It is believed that intellectual development is directly related to human consciousness, imagination, and thinking. At the same time, a person's intellect includes various functions. That is, the mental capacity in a person, as I said, mindset and culture. When all of this goes together smoothly, the development of a person's intellectual development begins to grow.

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